

THE ARTISTIC EXPRESSION OF WOMEN AND SOCIETY RELATIONS IN EUDORA WELTY'S "WHY I LIVE AT THE P.O."

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes Eudora Welty's "Why I Live at the P.O." as a representation of women's experiences in the American South. Through examination of sisterly conflict and family dynamics, the study reveals how Welty critiques patriarchal structures, traditional gender roles, and the limited agency available to Southern women in the early 20th century. The protagonist Sister's move to the post office symbolizes both personal alienation and the quest for female independence within a restrictive social environment.

No matter how many centuries pass, humanity remains at the center of literature, and their destiny, searches, struggles, and most importantly, aspirations on the path of spiritual elevation always remain the core theme of the finest works. In world literature, writer Eudora Welty, who holds a special significance with her invaluable creativity, also analyzes humanity and its life philosophy in her works. Particularly in stories such as "Why I Live at the P.O.", "Clytie", and "Flowers for Marjorie" from the author's collection "A Curtain of Green", the value and worth of human beings, their place in society, and the expression of family relationships are reflected. The social degradation during the Civil War that took place in the USA in the 19th century and the Great Depression during World War II, people's love for life, and depictions of fading hope for the future found their manifestation in almost all of the writer's works. During this period, the intensification of the industrial revolution in the country, unemployment, and the inevitable roots of the patriarchal system caused many writers to promote the "American idea" through their independence and independent thinking in society, striving to find their place. The heroes in Eudora Welty's works, who created productively in the early 20th century, also became the center of exactly such themes. The author's story "Why I Live At the P.O.", written in 1941, is considered a work that reveals the complex aspects of family relationships in the American South in its own unique humorous style. Through this story, the writer attempted to illuminate the contradictions, misunderstandings, and psychological states in southern families through delicate portrayals.

A number of scholars in the field of literary studies have analyzed Eudora Welty's work from various perspectives. In particular, Professor Catherine Helen Chengges in her research

“A Eudora Welty Checklist, 1986-2008” notes that Eudora Welty revealed the complex system in southern families, especially the competition among women, their place in the family, and their struggle for their dreams and aspirations on life's path through subtle humorous interpretation.

Literary scholar Patricia Meyer Spacks advanced the idea that “In the story, the main character Sister actually appears not as a targeted victim, but as a narrator who distorts her own lifestyle and relationships, and such women are frequently encountered in southern families. Through this work, Eudora Welty shows us that family conflicts often arise from bilateral misunderstandings.” The story illuminates psychological aspects in family relationships, such as envy, prejudice, mutual respect, and elements of communication culture. The story begins with the words of the main character Sister. As a narrator, she begins her story as follows:

“I was getting along fine with Mama, Papa-Daddy and Uncle Rondo until my sister Stella-Rondo just separated from her husband and came back home again.”

This sentence shows that the real origin of family conflicts throughout the entire story is Sister's sister Stella-Rondo's separation from her marriage and return home. Through this story, Eudora Welty takes a deep look at the complex system of family values in the southern states and spousal relationships. The consequences of separation in the lives of the work's main characters indicate not only personal tragedy but also the degradation that emerges throughout society. Throughout the story, the author manifests not only the direct impact of separation but also the wide-ranging social consequences that this event brings about, such as the atmosphere of distrust among people, emotional loneliness, and the breaking of family ties.

The writer attempts to show the complex relationship dynamics in southern families by depicting the conflicting relationships between the main characters Sister and Stella-Rondo. The competition, envy, and hostility between the sisters has deeper social roots than ordinary family disagreements, and it indicates that at the core of this contradiction lies the hidden social hierarchy existing among women in southern society, limited opportunities, and the obligation to submit to traditional gender roles. Against the background of family conflicts depicted in the work, along with the clash of personal interests, there also lie eroding cultural values and social expectations. The author skillfully demonstrates such habits in southern families as highly emotional relationships, the culture of keeping secrets, and hiding internal contradictions to maintain external reputation.

Furthermore, through the story, Eudora Welty also explores society's attitude toward divorced women, child-rearing, and the changing nature of concepts of family loyalty. The development of events in the work shows the importance of the family institution in southern society, the strength of connections, and how these connections can fragment if conflicts are not resolved. Through this, the writer tells about separation and its negative consequences, which was one of the serious problems in families of her time.

American literary scholar Suzanne Marrs writes in her research “The Welty Collection: A Guide to the Eudora Welty Manuscripts and Documents”: “In *Why I Live at the P.O.*”, Eudora Welty depicts separation not simply as a family tragedy, but as an event that fragments the fabric of society. Through the image of Sister, she shows the complex situation of women

seeking their independence within the rigid social norms of southern society. Through Stella-Rondo's separation and her return to the family, Eudora Welty skillfully portrays the status and limited opportunities of women within the patriarchal system."

Because the work's main character Sister tells the story from her own perspective, she always considers herself to be right. The conflicts in the family force Sister to think: "There I was with the whole entire house on Stella-Rondo's side and turned against me."

In this sentence in the character's speech, which says that all family members took Stella-Rondo's side as if they were against me, one can see that she feels lonely and misunderstood in the family. The reason is that Sister's sister, who returned after her divorce, speaks ill of her to all family members throughout the story for her own benefit, because her sister gave her an appropriate reprimand. This situation clearly shows the complex psychological dynamics in southern families depicted in the work and the hidden contradictions in the fabric of relationships.

Sister's feeling of herself as a foreign person in the family in her internal experiences shapes her entire life philosophy. Her beginning of the story with "Why I Live at the P.O." is actually the final point of this alienation - it is considered an explanation of the spiritual path that led to the decision to completely separate from the family. In the conflict between Stella-Rondo and Sister, not just sisterly rivalry is manifested, but the clash of two different personality types, two different life positions and value systems. At the core of family members' shift to Stella-Rondo's side lies a complex structure of interrelationships such as the tradition in southern families of showing more attention and care to a newly arrived, especially troubled family member, the feeling of protecting a family member, and the sense of protecting family honor from the outside world. When Stella-Rondo returns after her divorce, the family tries to ease her personal tragedy, and in this process, Sister's insistence on her rightness is perceived as a factor that undermines the family's sense of unity. Throughout the story, although Sister tries to present herself as fighting for justice in her internal monologues, the exaggerations in her speech, sharp judgments, and subjective conclusions suggest that she is also guilty to some extent in the emergence of conflict in the family. In the southern mentality, discussing conflicts within the family in front of the public, especially a younger family member's quarrel with elders, is considered an uncomfortable situation, and precisely because of this, Sister's actions are perceived as an undesirable element in the family, causing everyone to be upset with her. Through this, Eudora Welty skillfully shows not only the psychological elements of family conflicts in the example of one family, but also the system of relationships in southern society in general, family values and traditions, their positive and negative aspects.

One of the most impactful episodes of the story is manifested in the depiction of the tension among family members on the Fourth of July, Independence Day, and their uncle named Uncle Rondo's addiction to alcohol. "Uncle Rondo took a hundred of Papa-Daddy's pills... I never seen him in such a fix." Through this episode, the further deepening of unhealthy relationships in the family is shown. In addition, Eudora Welty also skillfully depicts in the story the pressure that patriarchal society shows toward women. Stella-Rondo's separation and return, the complexity of being accepted by the local community, Sister's move to the post

office to preserve her independence - all of these reflect the struggle of southern women on the path of preserving their dignity and worth.

At the end of the story, after Sister moves to the post office, through the sentence "I want to stay here now and live in a world where I always feel happy," Eudora Welty manifests that the character has given up on family relationships, on people who don't understand her, and has found herself in solitude, and has equated such solitude with happiness. Just as in the works of other regional writers, the final solution of this story also consists of choosing a solitary lifestyle and through this discovering independent thought and self. Such an ending of the story has symbolic meaning, and the main character's move to the post office signifies that she is separated not only from her family but also from society. Thus, through this story, Eudora Welty wants to emphasize that family relationships are not only personal relationships but are also, in a broad sense, a fundamental link of social life.

In conclusion, it can be said that Eudora Welty gained fame as a writer of the US regional literature period with her unique works. Particularly, in her story "Why I live at the P.O.", issues such as inevitable views in a specific environment characteristic of regional literature, family conflicts, and women's place in small communities were analyzed. Behind the fact that the main character Sister is addressed in the story as nameless, simply as "sister," the author through such an image points to the situation of any women living in society. In this story, Eudora Welty boldly puts forward problems that are considered relevant for society without any hesitation.

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